

Resonantly Pumped Tunable 2 μm Lasers Based on Tm^{3+} - and Ho^{3+} -doped BaF_2 and SrF_2 Crystals

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Abstract: We report on the tunable 2- μm laser operation of singly Ho^{3+} -doped and $\text{Tm}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ -codoped BaF_2 and SrF_2 fluorite-type crystals under 1.68 μm or 1.94 μm resonant pumping. The broadest tuning range of 1960–2100 nm was achieved with $\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$ laser system.

1. Introduction

Laser radiation in the 1.9–2.2 μm spectral range is of significant interest for diverse applications. This spectral range overlaps with a local absorption maximum of liquid water, making it particularly suitable for medical and surgical procedures involving soft biological tissues. The depth of penetration can be selectively controlled by tuning the emission wavelength [1]. Simultaneously, the transparency of both the atmosphere and standard silica-based optical fibers in this region makes such radiation attractive for free-space and fiber-based optical communication. Moreover, several important molecular species, including CO_2 , NO_2 , and H_2O , exhibit strong absorption features in this spectral window, which is advantageous for environmental sensing and gas detection.

Efficient generation of radiation near 2 μm can be readily achieved using solid-state lasers based on trivalent thulium (Tm^{3+} , the ${}^3\text{F}_4 \rightarrow {}^3\text{H}_6$ transition) and holmium (Ho^{3+} , the ${}^5\text{I}_7 \rightarrow {}^5\text{I}_8$ transition) ions, either individually or in combination. Among the various host materials, alkaline-earth fluorides MF_2 (where M stands for Ca, Sr, or Ba) have attracted attention due to their high thermal conductivity, low phonon energies, and high solubilities of rare-earth ions [2,3]. However, substituting divalent host cations (M^{2+}) with trivalent dopants (Tm^{3+} or Ho^{3+}) necessitates charge compensation, typically leading to the formation of various optically active centers. These centers result in broadened and smoothed absorption and emission spectra, even at relatively low dopant concentrations. In addition, clustering of dopant ions enhances ion-ion interactions, which can have both beneficial and detrimental effects on the laser performance depending on the energy transfer dynamics [4].

In this work, we report on the 2- μm laser performance of singly Ho^{3+} -doped and $\text{Tm}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ -codoped fluorite-type crystals, SrF_2 and BaF_2 . Resonant (in-band) pumping was provided by either a laser diode emitting at 1.68 μm or a Tm-fiber laser operating at 1.94 μm . The study focuses on the tuning behavior and performance of these fluoride compounds.

2. Laser setup

The investigated $\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$, $\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{SrF}_2$, $\text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$, and $\text{Ho}:\text{SrF}_2$ crystals were grown at the CIMAP laboratory using the Stockbarger-Bridgman technique under inert ($\text{Ar} + \text{CF}_4$) atmosphere using graphite crucibles [5]. The codoped samples contained 3 at.% Tm^{3+} and 0.5 at.% Ho^{3+} , while the singly doped ones contained 0.5 at.% Ho^{3+} . The laser elements were cut from the central part of the as-grown boules (diameter: 8 mm, thickness: 5 – 6 mm), they were polished on both sides to laser grade quality with high parallelism and left uncoated.

All the studied crystals were first longitudinally pumped using a pulsed Tm-fiber laser (TLR-50-1940, *IPG Photonics*) emitting at 1938 nm (into the ${}^5\text{I}_7$ Ho^{3+} manifold), with 5 ms-long pulses at a repetition rate of 20 Hz. The pump radiation was focused into the crystals by a CaF_2 lens ($f = 200$ mm). Additionally, the codoped samples were pumped using a fiber-coupled (core diameter: 400 μm) laser diode (BrightLase® Ultra-100, *QPC*) emitting at 1680 nm (pumping into the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ Tm^{3+} state). The diode produced 10 ms pulses at 10 Hz, and its output was focused into the crystals by a 1:1 telescope consisting of two achromatic doublets ($f = 75$ mm). The pump beam entered the laser resonator through a flat pump mirror (PM). Two PM types were used depending on the pump source: for the Tm-fiber laser, a mirror with high transmission (HT) at 1.94 μm and high reflectivity (HR) in the 2.0–2.2 μm range; for the diode laser, with HT at 1.7 μm and HR at 1.9–2.2 μm . Two output couplers (OC) were used. For the free-running operation, the OC had a radius of curvature $r = 150$ mm and a reflectivity $R = 98\%$ at 1.9–2.1 μm . For wavelength-tunable operation, an OC with $r = 100$ mm and $R = 99.5\%$ in the same spectral range was employed.

The laser wavelength tuning was enabled using a birefringent filter (BRF) made of MgF_2 , a positive uniaxial crystal. The filter (1 mm thick, 20 mm in diameter) was inserted into the resonator at Brewster's angle between the active medium and the OC. Wavelength selection was controlled by rotating the BRF around an axis perpendicular to its surface.

3. Laser performance

At first, the laser performance of the studied crystals was studied in the free-running regime, without the Lyor filter in the cavity. Table 1 summarizes the key laser parameters obtained under pumping at 1938 nm and 1680 nm. BaF_2 -based crystals generally outperformed their Sr counterparts, showing lower thresholds and higher slope efficiencies. This is due to the weaker energy-transfer upconversion (ETU, $^5\text{I}_7 + ^5\text{I}_7 \rightarrow ^5\text{I}_8 + ^5\text{I}_6$) in $\text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$ as compared to its Sr and Ca counterparts [5]. Codoping with Tm^{3+} slightly deteriorated laser performance in case of 1938-nm pumping, likely due to energy back-transfer to Tm^{3+} . However, it also enables efficient resonant pumping at 1680 nm.

Table 1. Laser performance of singly Ho^{3+} -doped and $\text{Tm}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ -codoped BaF_2 and SrF_2 crystals under resonant pumping.

Laser medium	$\text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$	$\text{Ho}:\text{SrF}_2$	$\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$	$\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{SrF}_2$	$\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$	$\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{SrF}_2$
Pumping wavelength [nm]	1938	1938	1938	1938	1680	1680
Slope eff. (vs. absorbed power) [%]	35	24	25	14	26	22
Threshold abs. power amplitude [W]	0.28	0.47	0.34	0.69	0.49	1.2

Continuous wavelength tuning was achieved with all the crystals studied. The tuning curves are presented in Fig. 1, comparing the behavior for BaF_2 - and SrF_2 -based crystals either singly doped with Ho^{3+} (pumped at 1938 nm) and codoped with Tm^{3+} and Ho^{3+} (pumped at both 1938 nm and 1680 nm). Tm^{3+} codoping has a minor impact on the spectral profile and width of the tuning curves under Ho resonant pumping. In contrast, pumping at 1680 nm (Tm in-band pumping) enabled the use of cavity mirrors with broader reflectivity bandwidths and lower losses, resulting in an extension of the tuning range towards shorter wavelengths for both host materials. This effect was particularly pronounced for $\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$, for which the tuning range nearly doubled. When comparing the two host materials, the tuning characteristics were similar, but BaF_2 -based crystals exhibited a blue shift of the tuning curves related to the weaker crystal-field strength for rare-earth ion clusters in this compound. The broadest tuning range of 140 nm (1960–2100 nm) was achieved with the $\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$ crystal pumped at 1680 nm.

Fig. 1. Tuning curves of Ho- and Tm,Ho-doped (a) BaF_2 and (b) SrF_2 crystals under resonant pumping.

4. Conclusion

To conclude, singly Ho^{3+} doped and $\text{Tm}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ codoped BaF_2 crystals appear highly promising for broadly tunable lasers around 2.1 μm under resonant pumping into Tm or Ho manifolds. In the present work, a $\text{Tm}, \text{Ho}:\text{BaF}_2$ laser is tuned across 1960–2100 nm. We believe that further optimization of the laser efficiency which seems to be impacted by the detrimental ETU from the Ho^{3+} upper laser level (this ETU process is enhanced in rare-earth ion clusters) is possible by engineering the cluster composition, *i.e.*, by introducing optically inactive “buffer” ions.

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